

Ion-Solvent Interactions in Aqueous Solution of Salicylate Ion and Salicylic Acid

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Relative viscosities of aqueous solutions of salicylic acid and its lithium, sodium, potassium, rubidium and ammonium salts have been measured in the temperature range 25-35° in which the viscosity B-coefficient of the salicylate ion increases with temperature indicating a net structure breaking effect. Salicylic acid is a structure maker since its B value decreases with rise in temperature. The B values of salicylic acid and salicylate ion are smaller than those of benzoic acid and benzoate ion, suggesting a probable involvement of the *ortho*-hydroxyl group in depolymerizing the solvent structure. This has been confirmed by studying the viscosities of sodium *o*-anisate in the same temperature range. At any given temperature the B-coefficient of *o*-anisate ion is greater than that of salicylate ion and it decreases with increasing temperature. No unique value can be assigned to the ionic viscosity B-coefficient of the salicylate ion at any particular temperature since B values depend on the nature of the cation partner establishing the cation sensitive structural modification of the water structure by the salicylate ion.

STUDIES on the viscosity B-coefficients of aqueous solutions of acetic acid and alkali metal acetates by various workers^{1,2} show that the B-coefficient of acetate ion (B=0.25) is much larger than that of acetic acid molecule (B=0.12). It has been suggested^{3,4} that this is due to an enhanced order producing nature of the acetate ion and not to any effect of size, since the acetic acid molecule is almost of identical size with the acetate ion. Similar behaviour has also been observed in aqueous solution for benzoic acid molecule and benzoate ion⁵. In the present paper we report the results of viscosity measurements on aqueous solution of salicylic acid⁶ and its Li-, Na-, K-, Rb- and NH₄-salts in the temperature range 25-35°, for making a direct comparison with the results observed in acetic acid-acetate ion and benzoic acid-benzoate ion systems. The purpose of the present investigation is to examine whether the introduction of a hydroxyl group in the *ortho* position of benzoic acid molecule influences or not the solvent structure and consequently the solute-solvent interaction of the resulting acid and the anion of the acid. To elucidate the role of the hydroxyl group in the *ortho* position in the solute-solvent interaction, it was blocked by methylation and the viscosity of sodium *o*-methoxy benzoate has also been studied in the temperature range 25-35°.

Experimental

Pure crystalline salicylic acid was used for the preparation of alkali metal salicylates. Equivalent amounts of salicylic acid and AnalaR grade alkali metal carbonates were mixed in a minimum volume of water to obtain a clear solution (sometimes a little warming was necessary) from which the salt was

slowly crystallized out. The repeatedly crystallized product was finally washed several times with distilled ether and dried. Stock solutions of alkali metal salicylates were prepared from the dried salts by direct weighing. Solutions of varying concentrations were then prepared from the stock by dilution. Densities of the solutions were measured by a calibrated weld type pycnometer (volume 40 ml), provided with a graduated stem fitted with a standard joint stopper at its upper end. All viscosity measurements were made in a specially designed high flow time Ostwald viscometer placed in a thermostat regulated within $\pm 0.005^\circ$. Efflux times of solutions measured by a $\frac{1}{10}$ th second stopwatch and reproducible within ± 0.2 seconds were averaged. For the calibration of the viscometer the observed flow times of freshly prepared triple distilled water at two different temperatures, viz., 30 and 35° were 867.8 and 785.5 seconds, respectively. The viscometer constants were determined according to

$$\frac{\eta}{d} = A't - B'/t \quad \dots (1)$$

where η (CP) is the viscosity, d the density (g. ml⁻¹) and t the flow time in seconds. The viscometer constants A' and B' are found to be 9.299×10^{-4} and 5.21109, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The experimental results of the relative viscosities of the aqueous solutions of the salicylates and salicylic acid have been analysed by the Jones-Dole⁷ equation

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + AC^{1/2} + BC \quad \dots (2)$$

where η/η_0 is the relative viscosity, C the molar concentration, A and B the constants characteristic of the electrolyte and have been graphically estimated from the intercepts and slopes respectively of the

plots $\eta_{sp}/C^{1/2}$ vs $C^{1/2}$ as shown in Figs. 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively. Linear plots according to equation (2) are obtained in all the cases studied. The results of A- and B-coefficients are recorded in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Plot of η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C} .

- | | |
|----------------------------|--|
| ○ Sodium salicylate at 25° | ◐ Sodium <i>orthomethoxy</i> benzoate at 35° |
| □ " " " 30° | ◑ " " " 25° |
| △ " " " 35° | |

Fig. 2. Plot of η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C} .

- | |
|-------------------------------|
| ○ Potassium salicylate at 25° |
| □ " " " 30° |
| △ " " " 35° |

Fig. 3. (a) Rubidium salicylate at 25° ○
 " " " 30° □
 Fig. 3. (b) Salicylic acid " 30° □
 " " " 35° Δ

Fig. 4. Plot of η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C} .
 Lithium salicylate ○ at 25°; Δ at 30°; □ at 35°
 Ammonium ,, ○ at 25°; Δ at 35°.

TABLE I—VISCOSITY A- AND B-COEFFICIENTS OF ALKALI METAL SALICYLATES, B-COEFFICIENT OF SALICYLATE ION AND ENERGY OF ACTIVATION FOR VISCOUS FLOW OF SALICYLATE ION

Solute	$A_{salt} (25^\circ)$		B_{salt}			B_{anion}			ΔE^\ddagger 25°
	Theoretical	Observed	25°	30°	35°	25°	30°	35°	
Li-salicylate	0.010	-0.005	0.472	0.474	0.488	0.322	0.330	0.349	-259 cal
Na-salicylate	0.0087	0.0115	0.368	0.379	0.394	0.282	0.293	0.309	-308 "
K-salicylate	0.0071	0.0060	0.260	0.280	0.300	0.267	0.281	0.295	-349 "
Rb-salicylate	0.0069	0.0070	0.283	0.270	—	0.263	0.293	—	-586 "
NH ₄ -salicylate	0.007	0.0000	0.308	—	0.306	0.31	—	0.308	—
Na-o-anisate	—	0.0000	0.593	—	0.549	0.509	—	0.464	+484 "
Salicylic acid	—	—	—	0.17	0.151	—	—	—	—

Concentrations of salts used are in the range 0.002 to 0.07 molar.

The theoretical values of the viscosity A-coefficients at 25°, calculated according to Falkenhagen-Vernon⁸ equation, are found to be 0.0087, 0.0071 and 0.0069 for Na-, K- and Rb-salicylates, respectively. The agreement between the calculated and the observed A values (Column 2, Table 1) is fairly good. In case of Li-salicylate at 25°, the observed A-coefficient is negative. Negative A-coefficients have been observed by Kay *et al*⁹ in some aqueous tetraalkyl ammonium salt solutions, by Yao and Benion¹⁰ in their studies on the viscosity of electrolytes in DMSO and by Blokhra *et al*¹¹ in connection with their studies on the viscosity of electrolytes in mixed solvents.

The B values of the salicylate ion (B_{anion}) at different temperatures have been calculated assuming the additive property^{1,2} of the total B-coefficient and are recorded in column 4 of Table 1. The values of B_{salt} and B_{anion} recorded in columns 3 and 4 of Table 1 show that both of them increase with increasing temperature suggesting that the salts as well as the salicylate ion are manifesting structure breaking behaviour in aqueous solution unlike the structure producing behaviour of acetate^{1,2} and benzoate⁶ ions observed in aqueous solution. At any given temperature the B-coefficient of the salicylate ion is greater than that of salicylic acid measured at all the temperatures. This confirms partly the behaviour observed in acetic acid-acetate ion and benzoic acid-benzoate ion systems. As outlined in the introduction it cannot be attributed to any intrinsic size difference.

On the other hand salicylic acid molecule shows structure making behaviour since its B value decreases with increasing temperature. Compared to benzoic acid molecule, salicylic acid has a lower B value than that of benzoic acid molecule⁶ at 30°. This suggests that apart from any consideration of what has been happening at the carboxylate end, the hydroxyl group, by virtue of its capacity towards hydrogen bonding with the bulk water molecules, cleaves the cage of the water structure present around the benzene ring where the hydration may be expected to be hydrophobic due to the appreciably large size of the benzene ring¹². Wen and Saito¹³ have shown that the B-coefficient of tetra-(2-hydroxyethyl) ammonium ion is lower than that of tetrapropyl ammonium ion of similar size, suggesting that the introduction of an hydroxyl group into the alkyl group destroys the hydrophobic character of the alkyl chains.

From an inspection of the data in column 4 of Table 1 it will not be prudent to assign any unique value to the ionic viscosity B-coefficient of the salicylate ion at any particular temperature since B_{anion} values depend on the cation partner and decrease systematically from Li to Rb at all the temperatures. This observation of cation sensitiveness of the B value of the salicylate ion indicates that the resultant structure of aqueous solution of alkali metal salicylates are built up cooperatively by both the cation and anion. The B-coefficient of K-salicylate

at 25°, obtained by Yasuda and Mizutani¹⁴, is 0.31 while the value obtained in the present study is 0.26 at the same temperature. Following Nightingale Jr. and Benck¹⁵, the energy of activation for viscous flow for the salicylate ion at 25° has been calculated and is found to be -259, -308, -349 and -586 cal for Li-, Na-, K- and Rb-salicylate solutions, respectively. This also establishes the cation sensitive structure breaking behaviour of the salicylate ion in the order $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Rb}^+$. Conversely it can be stated that in aqueous solutions of alkali metal salicylates the extent of structure produced by the salicylate ion has the following increasing order: $\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Rb}^+$. This behaviour is expected on the basis of the "localised hydrolysis" model¹⁶ of ion-solvent interaction since salicylic acid is a weak acid. According to this model the B values at any particular temperature should decrease systematically from Li to Rb. This type of behaviour has been observed in aqueous solutions of alkali metal acetates which show an excess energy of activation that depends on the nature of the cation and follows the order $\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$ in complete accord with the localised hydrolysis model of Harned and Robinson¹⁶.

From the observed temperature dependence of the B-coefficient of Na-*o*-methoxy benzoate it can be concluded that *o*-methoxy benzoate ion is manifesting structure making behaviour since its B value decreases with rise of temperature. In this anion, the -OCH₃ group cannot form any intra- or intermolecular hydrogen bonds whereas the -OH group in salicylate ion can form both types of hydrogen bonds. Therefore, it may reasonably be supposed that the capacity of the -OH group in the *ortho* position towards hydrogen bond formation leads to the unusual behaviour of the salicylate ion in aqueous solution. Similar behaviour has been noticed in the case of anthranilate ion¹⁷.

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